

Governance for Ice Preservation Initiatives

Report on September 21, 2024, Workshop

Background

[Ice Preservation](#) is dedicated to evaluating the feasibility of slowing the slide of West Antarctic glaciers by removing or refreezing the water at their base, as happened historically with the Kamb Ice Stream. If feasible, slowing the slide of those massive glaciers could slow the rate of sea level rise, buying time for lasting curbs on greenhouse gases. Whether the Kamb shutdown can be induced elsewhere is a novel research question. Ice Preservation seeks to address it with scientifically rigorous and socially acceptable research.

To achieve those foundational goals, we have hosted two workshops, each engaging individuals with diverse perspectives on the initiative's technical feasibility and social acceptability. The [first workshop](#) focused on technical aspects of ice preservation projects, including glacier bonding. The second workshop focused on social acceptability.

Given the logistical challenges of Antarctic research, preliminary research is planned for northern glaciers. All those glaciers are on land sacred to local communities, meaning that any research must be co-produced with their members – respecting their culture, seeking ways to bring local benefit, and honoring their contribution to global problems not of their making. Similarly, many people around the world care deeply about the fate of Antarctica, including its ecosystems, role in the global environment, and spiritual importance – hence are concerned about the interventions that basic research might promote or discourage.

Hoping to incorporate an appropriately broad range of perspectives, workshop participants were asked to contribute to one of three group discussions: The Northern Regions, The Southern Ocean, and Our Shared Earth. Plenary sessions provided technical, legal, and cultural knowledge, as shared background for participants.

We did not seek consensus, but constructive conversation regarding ways to ensure that both the process and product of the research were scientifically sound and socially acceptable. We are grateful to all those who shared their time, energy, and wisdom at

the workshop, as well as those who were unable to attend, but helped with organizing it and assimilating its work. We are especially grateful to our rapporteurs, whose notes and summaries we shared with members of each group. This brief report on the three groups is meant to give a feeling for the lively exchanges at the workshop and afterward.

The Northern Regions

All field research happens somewhere. Potential locations may have sacred value to one or more peoples. Knowledge of those places is part of those peoples' intellectual property. Research building on that knowledge may promote or forestall future extraction of knowledge or material resources (e.g., mining, tourism). It may impose direct costs (e.g., environmental damage, access roads) and opportunity costs, from preventing competing uses. It may recognize or discount indigenous knowledge. It may honor or compel contributions for the global good.

The social acceptability of any research project depends on its process as well as its product. That process reveals how scientists treat others, when designing a study and sharing its results. It can erode or enhance other parties' standing and ability to participate in that study and related ones. It can create expectations for future engagement that are or are not fulfilled. Ideally, it can create a virtuous circle of increasing empowerment, increasing the opportunities for co-creating research projects that serve both scientists and communities.

The Southern Ocean

Although no one lives in Antarctica permanently, it is home to wildlife and precious ecosystems. Antarctica is also a crucial component of the Earth's climate system; what happens there affects people everywhere. Melting glaciers contribute to sea level rise, which poses an existential peril to low-lying island nations and a catastrophic peril to all coastal communities and ecosystems. Each increment increases the destructive power of storm surges and groundwater salinization. Reducing the rate of Antarctic melting would, thus, mobilize scientific resources to address problems disproportionately borne by communities and nations that have contributed relatively little to climate change. The social acceptability of that science will depend on its rigor, transparency, and scope – including how it addresses ecological impacts and distributional effects.

Various international bodies have formal and informal jurisdiction over the conduct of research in Antarctica. Their early and continuing input can facilitate the development of research plans worthy of approval and create the supporting evidence needed for the

evaluation. Proactive interaction with them can create communication channels with the constituencies that they represent. It can create the sustained contact needed to build warranted trust. Legal expertise is needed to identify the relevant authorities and their procedures. Political wisdom is needed to identify those bodies that can (or should) inform the judgments needed when formal rules are applied.

Our Shared Earth

Projects with global implications will be judged in the court of global public opinion, whose informal verdicts will have diffuse impacts on whether they are funded, permitted, supported, or castigated. These public opinions can defeat worthy projects and sustain dubious ones. Projects will be judged by what they propose and do, and by how they propose and do it. Clumsy communications and non-transparent behavior can erode trust if interpreted as ignoring or disrespecting interested parties. It can also leave a vacuum for others to fill, perhaps with mis- or disinformation.

Sustained proactive, two-way communication can improve a project, by giving it a better story to tell, and helping it to tell that story, by creating trusted communication channels. Communication requires coordination across messages, so that they are coherent while addressing the concerns of diverse audiences. It requires adapting to its audiences' normal communication media. It requires coordination so that the science can respond to public concerns and communications remain faithful to the evolving sciences. It requires the professional expertise needed to design, test, and disseminate messages effectively while providing situational awareness to project leadership.

Mutual Dependence

Success in each of these domains will promote success in the others. Local communities will want to know that the project has a pathway to using foundational field research on its glaciers responsibly. Stewards of the Southern Ocean will want to know that the project has engaged local communities and global opinion appropriately. Supporters and critics in global civil society will want to know what milestones and controversies might lie ahead. The goal of governance is fewer, but better, conflicts, focused on legitimate differences of opinion, while avoiding needless misunderstandings.

Other Information

Funding

Funding for the Workshop was provided by the Stanford Doerr School of Sustainability Engagement Grant Program, Carnegie Mellon University, and personal contributions from workshop organizers.

Workshop conveners and organizers

Robert Axelrod, Vinton Cerf, Stephen Crocker, Baruch Fischhoff, Alex Luebke, Ken Mankoff, Kim Stanley Robinson, Jenny Suckale, Lexi Wright

Workshop report prepared by

Baruch Fischhoff, Jenny Suckale

Appendix A: List of Participants*

Group 1: The Northern Regions

- **Wai Yin Cheung**, PhD Student, Queen's University
- **Stephen Crocker**, Internet Pioneer
- **Meda DeWitt**, Lingít traditional healer
- **Ellen Haaslahti**, Head of Communications, Operaatio Arktis
- **Natalie Herbert**, Research Scientist, Stanford University
- **Kenneth H. O. Høegh**, Head of the Greenland Representation/ Minister, Washington DC
- **Ken Mankoff**, Senior Scientist, NASA
- **Angella Ndaka**, Critical AI scholar and thought leader
- **Kerry Nickols**, Senior Program Officer, Ocean Visions
- **Anni Pokela**, Strategic Planner, Operaatio Arktis
- **Rachel Ruckstuhl-Mann**, Movement artist
- **Heather Sauyaq Jean Gordon**, Sauyaq Solutions
- **Gabrielle Wong-Parodi**, Assistant Professor, Stanford University

Group 2: The Southern Ocean

- **Robert Axelrod**, Professor Emeritus, University of Michigan
- **Evan Bloom**, Senior Advisor, Centre for Ocean and the Arctic, Arctic University of Norway

- **Charlie Corbett**, Lawyer and legal researcher on climate change
- **David Holland**, Professor, New York University
- **Deneb Karentz**, US Delegate, Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research
- **Alex Luebke**, Technologist
- **Francesca Marzatico**, Lecturer, University of Otago
- **Jekope Ramala Maiono**, Lecturer, University of Otago
- **Edward Parson**, Professor, University of California, Los Angeles
- **Katie Pogi**, Senior Scientific Officer, Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, Samoa
- **Katharina Ruckstuhl**, Associate Professor/Dean Māori, Otago Business School
- **Karen Scott**, Professor, University of Canterbury
- **Leigh Stearns**, Professor, University of Pennsylvania
- **Jenny Suckale**, Associate Professor, Stanford University
- **Julia Wellner**, Professor, University of Houston
- **Violet Wulf-Saena**, Founder and Executive Director, Climate Resilient Communities

Group 3: Our Shared Earth

- **Clara Botto**, Director of Outreach, Alliance for Just Deliberation on Solar Geoengineering
- **Matthew Daniels**, Senior Advisor, Office of Net Assessment

- **Rajashree (Tri) Datta**, Assistant Professor, TU Delft, Netherlands
- **Baruch Fischhoff**, Professor, Carnegie Mellon University
- **Maya Fischhoff**, Senior Advisor, Network for Business Sustainability
- **Mizan Khan**, Lead Author, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- **Sabrina McCormick**, Sociologist and filmmaker
- **April Melvin**, Staff Lead, Polar Research Board, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine
- **Janos Pasztor**, formerly Executive Director, Carnegie Climate Governance Initiative
- **Kim Stanley Robinson**, Science fiction writer
- **Ben Strauss**, President and CEO, Climate Central
- **Kate Ricke**, Associate Professor, University of California, San Diego

*Some additional participants attended but did not wish to be named.

Appendix B: Workshop Guidelines

Statement of Principles

Alarmed by the rapid deterioration of glaciers worldwide, we believe that there is value in an open discussion of research related to the feasibility and social acceptability of interventions that could help preserve them.

Glacier preservation is not an alternative to reducing greenhouse gases drastically. It is a stopgap measure intended to slow the rate of sea-level rise and protect glacial environments until greenhouse gas pollution has been controlled.

We are committed to:

- evaluating any intervention's potential physical, biological, and social costs, risks, and benefits, and identifying research that can reduce critical uncertainties;
- engaging individuals with the diverse backgrounds needed for careful evaluations;
- bringing those individuals together in mutually respectful discussions, enabling them to understand one another's perspectives;
- communicating our work proactively and transparently, inviting comments;
- having no foregone conclusions, regarding the feasibility or social acceptability of any specific intervention or any intervention at all;
- creating a process suited to examining any large-scale project that would change the natural world, even if done to protect it; and
- giving all parties the opportunity to learn from each other.

We recognize the challenges of sustaining such dialogues, and the need for adaptive management. We welcome your feedback and participation.

Working Group Goals

The Northern Regions Working Group

Session 1: What Does Social Acceptability Mean in the Northern Regions?

- (1) Whom must we engage, at different stages of a project, respecting their potential contributions, right to participate, and life constraints? How does that engagement affect standing in other projects and participation demands?
- (2) What forms of engagement are suitable to different parties and project stages? What forms of reward are appropriate and inappropriate for parties with different stakes and resources? How should such participation be supported? What sources of distrust must be proactively addressed?
- (3) What cultural, social, economic, political, physical, and environmental impacts must be considered when planning possible research projects? What local impacts might we not be aware of? What is an appropriate time frame and geographical scope?

Session 2: What Processes Should We Follow?

- (1) How can we honor and integrate local and indigenous knowledge with traditional glaciology field work on an ongoing basis? What issues must be resolved collaboratively, and how can we achieve that?
- (2) How should we select locations for field studies? How can local communities or regional groups best be involved in site selection?
- (3) How can we manage field studies in ways that ensure their quality, safety, and contribution to local communities? How do we ensure continuing two-way communication as projects evolve and results emerge?
- (4) How can we represent insights from field studies in ways that reflect diverse viewpoints and interpretation, recognizing that scientific publications conventionally privilege some forms of evidence? How can we ensure that our communication is appropriate, relevant, and interpreted as intended?

Session 3: What Should Our Next Steps Be?

The Southern Ocean Working Group

Session 1: What Does Social Acceptability Mean in The Southern Ocean?

(1) Whom must we engage at each stage of the project? In addition to the legal framework of the Antarctic Treaty, which NGOs, regional associations, and indigenous groups should we consult? What issues concern them and which should we address? How can we best connect to them?

(2) What main issues should we address proactively? What environmental, social, and economic impacts should we assess as part of planning and conducting research projects, at local, regional and global scales?

(3) What broader benefits should we consider in the research and the research enterprise (e.g., insights into subglacial ecosystems, new research methods)?

Session 2: What Processes Could We Follow?

(1) How should we prepare now for a potential request for Antarctic field work several years away, informed by research in the Northern Region? How should we prepare for possible changes in Antarctic governance processes?

(2) How should we document and share our work to ensure transparency? How should we anticipate the needs and concerns of parties whose jurisdictional concerns only emerged as the project developed?

(3) How should we develop transparent codes of research conduct for research (e.g., an independent “stewardship board” overseeing potential studies, commitment to preregistration and open data)?

Session 3: What Should Our Next Steps Be?

Shared Earth Discussion Group

Session 1: What Does Social Acceptability Mean at the Global Scale?

(1) Who are the key parties who will want to know about the project and have the opportunity to provide input (e.g., scientists, activists, policy makers)? How do they prefer to communicate? What information does each want us to create and share? How do we warrant trust from parties who will only engage later?

(2) What issues do our communications need to address (e.g., the perceived moral hazard threat in a project not directly aimed at decarbonization; our focus on research, motivated by possible interventions; our goal of informing intervention decisions, without prejudging feasibility and acceptability; our relationship to other intervention projects)?

(3) What are potential pitfalls in our engagement process (e.g., not testing messages before release, using inappropriate tone and framing, neglecting emotions, neglecting visuals, using people's time poorly, not responding promptly)?

Session 2: What Processes Could We Follow?

(1) How can we build on the personal connections made at the workshop, including the contacts made with people who could not come but were interested (e.g., advisory panels, groups liaisons, working groups, input channels, website)?

(2) How can we engage the scientific community in issues such as (a) allocating scarce government resources for basic science, (b) government vs. private funding, and (c) balancing passive and active roles (e.g., predict sea level vs. extracting implications for ice preservation interventions).

(3) How can we design and evaluate messages, and communication channels, suited to diverse audiences, including opportunities for feedback, that will enable us to learn and demonstrate our willingness to learn? How can we make two-way communication part of community building, for this project and others?

(4) How can we ensure that our own practices fulfill our vision? How can we preserve collaborative working relations as the project grows? How should we ensure sound scientific practices (e.g. peer review, preregistration, data sharing)?

Session 3: What Should Our Next Steps Be?